

COMPARISON OF SITAGLIPTIN VERSUS SULFONYLUREAS FOR TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

Dr Kalim Ullah Altaf¹, Dr Asim Saleem Sheikh², Dr Shumaila Israr³, Professor Khalida Ajmal⁴

¹Postgraduate Resident Medicine Department, District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala

² Associate Professor Medicine Department, District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala

³Classified Medical Specialist, PAC Hospital Kamra

⁴Professor Department of Pharmacology, Wah Medical College, National University of Medical Science, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

*kalim.ullah6768@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17283810>

Keywords

Type 2 diabetes mellitus, sitagliptin, sulfonylureas, hypoglycemia, randomized controlled trial, glycemic control, pharmacotherapy.

Article History

Received: 15 February 2025

Accepted: 25 March 2025

Published: 5 April 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Kalim Ullah Altaf

Abstract

Objective: To compare the outcome of sitagliptin versus sulfonylureas for treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted at DHQ Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala, involving 90 participants with newly diagnosed T2DM. Patients were randomly assigned to either sitagliptin (100 mg daily) or glipizide (100 mg daily) groups. The incidence of hypoglycemia, defined as blood glucose levels below 70 mg/dL, was recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25.0, with comparisons made using chi-square tests, and a p -value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: Sitagliptin users are slightly older on average (48.96 years) compared to Sulfonylurea users (45.64 years). There was 4:1 male-to-female ratio distribution in both groups. The incidence of hypoglycemia was significantly lower in the sitagliptin group (4.4%) compared to the sulfonylurea group (17.8%, $p=0.044$). Age, gender, BMI, and lifestyle factors influenced hypoglycemia occurrence, with higher rates observed in sedentary individuals and those employed in manual occupations. No significant differences were found in terms of hypertension, smoking, or dyslipidemia.

Conclusion: Sitagliptin is associated with a significantly lower incidence of hypoglycemia compared to sulfonylureas in the treatment of T2DM. This finding underscores the safety of sitagliptin, particularly for patients at higher risk for hypoglycemia, such as the elderly and those with sedentary lifestyles.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus refers to a collection of metabolic disorders marked by elevated blood glucose levels. People with diabetes have an increased risk of developing a number of serious life-threatening health problems, which results in higher medical care costs, reduced quality of life and increased mortality.⁽¹⁾ The

World Health Organization reports that some 415 million people worldwide live with diabetes. Global trends demonstrate a continuing growth in its prevalence at approximately 2.5 % per year.⁽²⁾ A substantial proportion of type 2 diabetes cases may be prevented through lifestyle modifications, such as

achieving and maintaining a healthy weight, following a balanced diet, engaging in regular physical activity, avoiding tobacco use, and limiting alcohol consumption. Most patients with type 2 diabetes have at least one complication, and cardiovascular complications are the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in these patients.⁽³⁾ Treatment of type 2 diabetes frequently involves multiple glucose-lowering drugs, including sulfonylureas like glibenclamide (glyburide), glipizide, and gliclazide. These medications lower blood glucose by stimulating the secretion of insulin in the body, thereby increasing insulin levels in the blood.⁽⁴⁾ Sitagliptin seems to maintain its positive effects on glycemia and fasting plasma insulin on the long term.⁽⁵⁾ Compared with sulfonylureas, Sitagliptin use resulted in minor weight loss, though the roughly 2 kg difference may not hold major clinical significance. Most other efficacy outcomes demonstrated similar changes. Further studies are needed to address longer-term effectiveness outcomes for sitagliptin compared to sulfonylureas as add-on to metformin.⁽⁶⁾

This study investigates the risk of hypoglycemia with Sitagliptin compared to Sulfonylureas in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Although both medications achieve similar glycemic control, Sitagliptin is associated with fewer side effects and better weight regulation, which may help reduce insulin resistance and enhance metabolic outcomes. Limited local data exist, yet both drug classes are widely prescribed in routine practice. By generating evidence specific to the local population, this study aims to support more informed treatment decisions, improve patient safety, and optimize therapeutic strategies in clinical settings

METHODOLOGY

After approval from ethical review committee, the randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Medicine, DHQ Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala, over a duration of 6 months (1st August 2024 to 31st January 2025). A sample size of 90 patients (45 in each group) was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, with 45 participants in each group. The calculation was based on a 5% significance level, 80% power of the study, and a hypoglycemia rate of 6.5% for Sitagliptin and 25.9% for sulfonylureas. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used for patient selection.

Inclusion criteria

included patients aged 30-60 years, both male and female, who were newly diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Exclusion criteria

consisted of patients already on anti-glycemic medications, pregnant females, patients requiring the addition of more than one drug to metformin monotherapy, or those with background therapies other than metformin monotherapy.

Informed consent was obtained prior to participation. Demographic details such as age, gender, BMI, history of smoking (more than 5 pack years), hypertension (BP <140/90 mmHg), dyslipidemia (total cholesterol >200 mg/dL), family history of diabetes, socioeconomic status, residence, occupation, working hours, and lifestyle were collected. Patients were randomly assigned to two groups using a random number table. Group A received 100 mg of sitagliptin daily, while Group B received 100 mg of glipizide (sulfonylurea) daily. During the follow-up, patients were instructed to monitor their blood glucose levels daily. Episodes of hypoglycemia, defined as a blood glucose level <70 mg/dL, were recorded.

Data were analyzed using SPSS v25.0. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the incidence of hypoglycemia. Chi-square test was applied to compare the incidence of hypoglycemia between both groups. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Additionally, data were stratified by variables such as age, gender, BMI, smoking history, hypertension, dyslipidemia, family history of diabetes, socioeconomic status, residence, occupation, and lifestyle. Post-stratification, the incidence of hypoglycemia was compared between groups using the chi-square test, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered significant.

RESULTS

The table compares two groups: Sitagliptin and Sulfonylurea users. Sitagliptin users are slightly older on average (48.96 years) compared to Sulfonylurea users (45.64 years). Both groups report similar working hours. The gender distribution is the same in both groups, with a 4:1 male-to-female ratio. Sitagliptin users have a slightly lower BMI (29.13) compared to Sulfonylurea users (29.73). Smoking

rates are similar, with a slightly lower percentage of smokers in the Sitagliptin group (22.2%) compared to Sulfonylurea users (24.4%). The presence of hypertension and dyslipidemia is almost the same in both groups. However, the Sulfonylurea group has a slightly higher percentage with a family history of Type 2 diabetes (55.6%) compared to Sitagliptin users (48.9%). In terms of socioeconomic status, a higher percentage of Sitagliptin users belong to the low-income category (35.6%) compared to Sulfonylurea users (22.2%). Most participants in both groups belong to the middle-income bracket. Both groups predominantly reside in urban areas, though the

Sitagliptin group shows a slightly higher percentage of rural residents (35.6%) compared to the Sulfonylurea group (37.8%). For lifestyle habits, the trend is similar, with a higher percentage of individuals in both groups having a sedentary lifestyle (55.6% in Sitagliptin and 60% in Sulfonylurea). The proportion of active individuals remains the same (33.3%) in both groups. In terms of profession, both groups have a larger share in professional/clerical/commerce roles (P/Cl/E/Com), with the Sulfonylurea group showing a slightly higher proportion in agriculture (13.3%) compared to Sitagliptin users (8.9%). Table-I

Table-I: Baseline characteristics of patients enrolled in the trial (n = 90)

		Sitagliptin	Sulfonylurea
		45	45
Age (Years)		48.96 ± 7.24	45.64 ± 6.33
Working Hours (Hours)		8.96±1.85	8.89±2.17
Gender (M:F)		4:1	4:1
BMI		29.13 ± 3.12	29.73 ± 3.03
Smoking		10(22.2%)	11(24.4%)
Hypertension		18(40%)	19(42.2%)
Dyslipidemia		16(35.6%)	16(35.6%)
Family History of T2 diabetes		22(48.9%)	25(55.6%)
Socioeconomic status	Low	16(35.6%)	10(22.2%)
	Middle	25(55.6%)	31(68.9%)
	High	4(8.9%)	4(8.9%)
Residence	Rural	16(35.6%)	17(37.8%)
	Urban	29(64.4%)	28(62.2%)
Life style	Active	15(33.3%)	15(33.3%)
	Exercise	5(11.1%)	3(6.7%)
	Sedentary	25(55.6%)	27(60%)
Profession	P/Cl/E/Com	23(51.1%)	24(53.3%)
	S/T/Sec/SM	15(33.3%)	12(26.7%)
	Agriculture	4(8.9%)	6(13.3%)
	House Wife	3(6.7%)	3(6.7%)

P: Professional, Cl: Clerical, E: Education, C: Commerce
S: Services, T: Transport, S: Security, Skilled Manual

In this study, the frequency of hypoglycemia was significantly higher with sulfonylurea than with sitagliptin (17.8% vs 4.4%, p=0.044). Across age groups, rates were higher with sulfonylurea except in participants aged 41–50 years. A similar pattern was seen among men. Among those who were overweight, hypoglycemia occurred in 9.5% on sulfonylurea vs

4.5% on sitagliptin; among those with obesity, 25% vs 5.3%, respectively (overall p=0.708). Smoking and hypertension showed no significant overall association; however, in non-hypertensive patients, hypoglycemia remained higher with sulfonylurea (23.1% vs 3.7%, p=0.050). Dyslipidemia, family history of type 2 diabetes, socioeconomic status, and

residential status were not significantly associated with hypoglycemia in either group. Participants with a sedentary lifestyle had higher rates with sulfonylurea (22.2% vs 0%, p=0.023), and those employed in

services/transport/security/skilled manual occupations also showed higher rates with sulfonylurea (33.3% vs 0%, p-value=0.028). Table-II

Table-II: Episode of hypoglycemia in both trial groups and when controlled for effect modifiers (n = 90)

			Sitagliptin	Sulfonylurea	p-value
			45	45	
			Yes	Yes	
Hypoglycemia			2 (4.4%)	8 (17.8%)	0.044
Variables	Categories	n (%)	Hypoglycemia		
Age (Years)	30-40	18 (20%)	0 (0%)	3 (23.1%)	0.522
	41-50	46 (51.1%)	1 (4.3%)	1 (4.3%)	-
	51-60	26 (28.9%)	1 (5.9%)	4 (44.4%)	0.034
Gender	Male	72 (80%)	1 (2.8%)	8 (22.2%)	0.028
	Female	18 (20%)	1 (11.1%)	0 (0%)	-
BMI	Normal	4 (4.4%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	-
	Overweight	43 (47.8%)	1 (4.5%)	2 (9.5%)	-
	Obese	43 (47.8%)	1 (5.3%)	6 (25%)	0.708
Smoking	Yes	21 (23.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (18.2%)	0.476
	No	69 (76.7%)	2 (5.7%)	6 (17.6%)	0.151
Hypertension	Yes	37 (41.11%)	1 (5.6%)	2 (10.5%)	-
	No	53 (58.89%)	1 (3.7%)	6 (23.1%)	0.050
Dyslipidemia	Yes	32 (35.6%)	1 (6.3%)	4 (25%)	0.333
	No	58 (64.45)	1 (3.4%)	4 (13.8%)	0.352
F/H (T2-DM)	Yes	47 (52.2%)	2 (9.1%)	6 (24%)	0.253
	No	43 (47.8%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0.210
SES	Low	26 (28.9%)	0 (0%)	1 (10%)	0.385
	Middle	56 (62.2%)	2 (8%)	7 (22.6%)	0.167
	High	8 (8.9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	-
Residence	Rural	33 (36.7%)	1 (6.3%)	3 (17.6%)	0.601
	Urban	57 (63.3%)	1 (3.4%)	5 (17.9%)	0.120
Life style	Active	30 (33.3%)	1 (6.7%)	1 (6.7%)	-
	Exercise	8 (8.9%)	1 (20%)	1 (33.3%)	-
	Sedentary	52 (57.8%)	0 (0%)	6 (22.2%)	0.023
Occupation	P/C/E/C	47 (52.2%)	2 (8.7%)	3 (12.5%)	-
	S/T/S/SM	27 (30%)	0 (0%)	4 (33.3%)	0.028
	Agriculture	10 (11.1%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	-
	House Wife	6 (6.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	-

DISCUSSION

The results of this study showed a significantly higher frequency of hypoglycemia in the Sulfonylurea group compared to the Sitagliptin group. i.e. (17.8% vs. 4.4%, p-value=0.044). Local and international studies have reported low risk of hypoglycemia with sitagliptin.⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾ Sitagliptin is the first DPP-4 inhibitor

approved for T2DM, having been utilized for over 15 years, offering robust HbA1c lowering and a low risk of hypoglycemia across diverse therapeutic regimens, and providing other benefits such as CV safety and the convenience of once-daily administration. It is applicable to a diverse range of patients with T2DM, both for primary and secondary prevention.⁽⁷⁾ A

recently published international study reported the frequency of hypoglycemia with Sitagliptin in type 2 diabetic patients to be as low as 0.3%.⁽¹⁰⁾ R. R. Shankar reported hypoglycemia rates of 6.2% with Sitagliptin and 27.8% with sulfonylurea in his study which is consistent with the results of this study.⁽¹¹⁾ Similar findings were reported by Masahiro Fukuda. He reported no change in hypoglycemia from baseline (3.3%) to 52 weeks post treatment (2.8%) and with combination therapy with sulfonylurea odds of hypoglycemia was significantly higher after 52 weeks. i.e. (OR=2.2., p-value<0.001).⁽¹²⁾ When considering hypoglycemia risk in type 2 diabetes, sitagliptin and

sulfonylureas differ significantly in both their mechanisms and the influence of patient characteristics. Sulfonylureas increase insulin secretion regardless of blood glucose levels, which can precipitate hypoglycemia, especially in susceptible individuals. In contrast, sitagliptin, a DPP-4 inhibitor, enhances insulin secretion in a glucose-dependent manner, resulting in a much lower risk of hypoglycemia when used alone. However, when sitagliptin is combined with sulfonylureas, the risk rises substantially due to additive effects on insulin secretion.⁽¹³⁾ Several patient characteristics influence the risk of hypoglycemia in those treated with sitagliptin and sulfonylureas for type 2 diabetes. The most robust evidence highlights the impact of age, gender, BMI, polypharmacy, and comorbidities, while data on smoking, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and family history are more limited. In this study across age groups (30-40 and 51-60 years), rates were higher with sulfonylurea except in participants aged 41-50 years. Older adults are at higher risk of hypoglycemia due to age-related decline in renal function and drug metabolism, which can lead to drug accumulation and prolonged hypoglycemic episodes. This is especially concerning in elderly patients with comorbidities such as dementia or renal impairment, where hypoglycemia can result in serious complications like falls, cognitive decline, or hospitalization. Clinically, sulfonylureas should be used cautiously in older adults, and alternative agents with lower hypoglycemia risk may be preferred.⁽¹⁴⁾ Sitagliptin's glucose-dependent mechanism means age has minimal impact on hypoglycemia risk. Even in elderly populations, DPP-4 inhibitors like sitagliptin are associated with a lower

risk of hypoglycemia, making them a safer choice for older adults.⁽¹⁴⁾ Male patients in this study experienced significantly higher frequency of hypoglycemia in sulfonylurea group.

However, among female patients no significant difference was seen. Gender differences have also been observed, with some studies with sulfonylurea suggesting women may be at higher risk, potentially due to differences in drug metabolism and body composition.⁽¹⁵⁾ No such risk was reported with Sitagliptin in the studies.⁽¹⁶⁾ Although BMI had no significant effect on hypoglycemia in study groups but obese patients in sulfonylurea group had higher frequency of hypoglycemia as compared sitagliptin group. BMI has little effect on hypoglycemia risk with sitagliptin. This supports its use in both lean and obese patients, especially when hypoglycemia avoidance is a priority.⁽¹⁶⁾ Lower BMI is associated with increased hypoglycemia risk, likely because individuals with less adipose tissue have reduced glycogen reserves, making it harder to recover from low blood sugar. Clinically, sulfonylureas should be used with caution in lean patients, and dose adjustments or alternative therapies may be warranted.⁽¹⁷⁾ This study found that smoking, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and a family history of type 2 diabetes did not significantly influence hypoglycemia in the treatment groups. Current research indicates that smoking, hypertension (HTN), dyslipidemia, and family history of diabetes do not have a significant or consistent impact on the risk of hypoglycemia for patients using either sitagliptin or sulfonylurea monotherapy. The primary risk factors for hypoglycemia remain medication type, age, renal function, BMI, and history of previous hypoglycemia episodes^(18, 19). While HTN is a common comorbidity in diabetes and may contribute to overall cardiovascular risk, it does not appear to directly affect hypoglycemia incidence with sitagliptin or sulfonylurea monotherapy. Management of dyslipidemia remains important for cardiovascular health, but it does not necessitate changes in hypoglycemia risk assessment for these therapies^(18, 19). None of the patient-related factors had a significant impact on the Sitagliptin group with respect to hypoglycemia, making it a safer option for treating type 2 diabetic patients. The study's limitations include a small sample size, short duration, and

potential confounding factors like diet and comorbidities. Additionally, the assessment of hypoglycemic episodes may lack consistency, and long-term outcomes were not evaluated due to the lack of follow-up.

CONCLUSION

The study results indicate that Sitagliptin is more effective than sulfonylurea, in terms of reducing hypoglycemia. However, factors such as age, gender, non-hypertensive patients, sedentary lifestyle, and certain occupations (services, transport, security, or manual labor) were linked to a higher incidence of hypoglycemic episodes with sulfonylurea.

REFERENCES

1. Safiri S, Karamzad N, Kaufman JS, Bell AW, Nejadghaderi SA, Sullman MJM, et al. Prevalence, Deaths and Disability-Adjusted-Life-Years (DALYs) Due to Type 2 Diabetes and Its Attributable Risk Factors in 204 Countries and Territories, 1990-2019: Results From the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*. 2022;13.
2. Kotwas A, Karakiewicz B, Zabielska P, Wieder-Huszla S, Jurczak A. Epidemiological factors for type 2 diabetes mellitus: evidence from the Global Burden of Disease. *Archives of Public Health*. 2021;79(1):110.
3. Zheng Y, Ley SH, Hu FB. Global aetiology and epidemiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus and its complications. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*. 2018;14(2):88-98.
4. Madsen KS, Kähler P, Kähler LKA, Madsbad S, Gnesin F, Metzendorf MI, et al. Metformin and second- or third-generation sulphonylurea combination therapy for adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2019;4(4):Cd012368.
5. Derosa G, D'Angelo A, Maffioli P. Sitagliptin in type 2 diabetes mellitus: Efficacy after five years of therapy. *Pharmacological research : the official journal of the Italian Pharmacological Society*. 2015;100.
6. Sharma M, Beckley N, Nazareth I, Petersen I. Effectiveness of sitagliptin compared to sulfonylureas for type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on metformin: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ open*. 2017;7(10):e017260.
7. Sethi B, John M, Pendurthi B, Dharmadhikari S, Markandeywar N, Khandhedia C, et al. Exploring the Role of Sitagliptin in the Management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus for the Elderly: A Narrative Review. *The Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*. 2025;73(4):e26-e32.
8. HUSSAIN S, MUSTAFA A, MUMTAZ A, SHAHEEN G, QAISER F, SOBAN M. Comparison of efficacy and safety of sitagliptin and glimepiride in treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *PJMHS*. 2021;15(10):2800-3.
9. Aravind SR, Ismail SB, Balamurugan R, Gupta JB, Wadhwa T, Loh SM, et al. Hypoglycemia in patients with type 2 diabetes from India and Malaysia treated with sitagliptin or a sulfonylurea during Ramadan: a randomized, pragmatic study. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 2012;28(8):1289-96.
10. Seaquist ER, Phillips LS, Ghosh A, Baker C, Bergenstal RM, Crandall JP, et al. Glycemia reduction in type 2 diabetes—Hypoglycemia outcomes: A randomized clinical trial. *PLoS one*. 2024;19(11):e0309907.
11. Shankar R, Xu L, Golm G, O'Neill E, Goldstein B, Kaufman K, et al. A comparison of glycaemic effects of sitagliptin and sulfonylureas in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2015;69(6):626-31.
12. Fukuda M, Doi K, Sugawara M, Mochizuki K. Efficacy and safety of sitagliptin in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a focus on hypoglycemia. *Journal of diabetes investigation*. 2019;10(2):383-91.

13. Saito T, Ohmura H, Nojiri S, Daida H. Impact of sitagliptin combination therapy and hypoglycemia in Japanese patients with type 2 diabetes: a multi-center retrospective observational cohort study. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Health Care and Sciences*. 2020;6.
14. Horii T, Atsuda K. 396-P: Investigating the Risk of Severe Hypoglycemia in Elderly Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes*. 2020.
15. Dimakos J, Cui Y, Platt R, Renoux C, Filion K, Douros A. 1136-P: A Population-Based Assessment of the Risk of Severe Hypoglycemia with Concomitant Use of Sulfonylureas and Peptidomimetic Dipeptidyl Peptidase-4 Inhibitors. *Diabetes*. 2022.
16. Horii T, Atsuda K. 396-P: Investigating the Risk of Severe Hypoglycemia in Elderly Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes*. 2020.
17. Dennis J, Henley W, Weedon M, Lonergan M, Rodgers L, Jones A, et al. Sex and BMI Alter the Benefits and Risks of Sulfonylureas and Thiazolidinediones in Type 2 Diabetes: A Framework for Evaluating Stratification Using Routine Clinical and Individual Trial Data. *Diabetes Care*. 2018;41:1844-53.
18. Silbert R, Salcido-Montenegro A, Rodríguez-Gutiérrez R, Katabi A, McCoy R. Hypoglycemia Among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Prevention Strategies. *Current Diabetes Reports*. 2018;18:1-16.
19. Fuchigami A, Shigiyama F, Kitazawa T, Okada Y, Ichijo T, Higa M, et al. Efficacy of dapagliflozin versus sitagliptin on cardiometabolic risk factors in Japanese patients with type 2 diabetes: a prospective, randomized study (DIVERSITY-CVR). *Cardiovascular Diabetology*. 2020;19.